

Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Program in Sports

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Abstract:

Physical education teachers, as key implementers of the Special Program in Sports (SPS), play a vital role in delivering meaningful learning experiences that develop learners into well-rounded 21st-century Filipino athletes capable of navigating both local and global sports contexts. This descriptive study aimed to assess the instructional skills of these teachers in curriculum, teaching, and assessment, grouped by variables such as sex, grade level, and sports specialization. Findings revealed that physical education teachers consistently demonstrated a high level of instructional skills across all evaluated areas, with no significant differences among groups. Recognizing the importance of continuous professional growth, the study highlights the value of capability-building plans to further empower these educators. To enhance skills—particularly in areas with lower scores—it proposes a comprehensive development program including seminar-workshops on innovative teaching methods like the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) model, benchmarking of best practices, ICT refresher courses for digital lesson delivery, and implementation of Independent Cooperative Learning (ICL) through remedial classes. These initiatives aim to strengthen teachers' expertise, improve teaching effectiveness, and ultimately maximize student outcomes in specialized sports education.

Keywords: Development Program, Instructional Skills, Physical Education Teachers

Introduction:

As an important learning venue, the Department of Education recognizes that the standard of instruction is very much linked to the effectiveness of student learning. It acknowledges that competent physical educators are instrumental in molding the educational experience and that good teaching is critical for promoting student understanding, participation, and general success in their studies.

The Department of Education in the Philippines issued DepEd Order No. 25, s 2015, which contains the Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports (SPS). The SPS program curriculum design provides a four-year secondary curriculum guided by the K to 12 Basic Education Program patterned after that of a regular high school with specialization in sports in individual, dual, and team sports. One of the primary objectives of implementing this program is to address the needs of talented students in the different sports disciplines in regular high schools, which can implement and sustain the program in terms of trained and equipped teachers, facilities, and equipment.

The commitments articulated in the MATATAG Agenda, DepEd has adopted DepEd Order (DO) No. 013, s: 2023, Adoption of the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) in the Department of Education. The reform process warrants an equivalent supportive focus on teacher quality, with high-quality teachers who are adequately equipped and prepared to assume the roles and functions of K-12 teachers.

Furthermore, research by Rayvin D. Pestano and Florante P. Ibarra (2021) highlights that a combination of factors influences an athlete's performance. These include the athlete's technical abilities, tactical understanding, physiological conditioning, and psychological or sociological traits. Additionally, the impact of coaches cannot be overlooked, as their teaching styles and overall competencies play a crucial role in shaping athletic success.

A technology-driven approach, such as the flipped classroom, positively impacts learning by creating a conducive environment for active student participation (Ambikapathy et al., 2020; Said, 2020; Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). Nevertheless, some Physical Education (PE) teachers have not fully embraced the idea and are still uncertain about its effectiveness in their particular context (Wasriep & Lajium, 2019).

Although its efficacy has been demonstrated, continuing new investigations and evaluations of the Special Program in Sports (SPS) in the Philippines are needed to prove its sustainability and long-term success (Philippine Social Science Journal, 2019). The essential success factors are good infrastructure, competent coaches, and a thoughtful plan.

PE educators are encountering several difficulties in their attempts to carry out the Special Program in Sports (SPS), which is characterized by its extensive syllabus and unfamiliarity with the particular professional domain. Schools have to give professional development opportunities to their staff in order to fill in the gaps in their skills.

The paper's primary purpose was to measure the instructional skills of PE teachers in the SPS domain. The main thrust is to reap the necessary information on localizing the curriculum, changing the learning activities, matching the assessments, and addressing the student's needs. The results will help teachers upgrade their skills in sports education and allow them to formulate a capability-building plan for educational supervisors and administrators with the common goal of improving teaching methodologies.

Current State of Knowledge

Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports. Education is a continuous journey that relies on the availability of competent teachers, who are essential in leading students toward accomplishing their learning goals. The Special Program in Sports (SPS) is a recognized and exhaustive syllabus woven into the K-12 education system. Accordingly, its main aim is to raise and sharpen the sports capacities of children who exhibit great potential in the various fields of the sports world. SPS is a vehicle through which students who are voluntarily devoted to the sports compass can acquire adequate customized training and educational experiences.

The program is designed to develop and improve athletic abilities, and it also makes the point that academic success is critical; hence, students are allowed to combine their love for sports with education. Through fit and specialized mentorship, frequent physical exercises, and competition participation, the SPS equips learners to become champions in their chosen sports while facing off against other players in events, such as college-level sports or professional games.

Besides training activities, the SPS syllabus often combines sports science, nutrition, and psychological training. Hence, students understand what it means to be successful in sports. Through providing a motivating atmosphere and the availability of facilities, the Special Program in Sports seeks to become the new role models for athletes and simultaneously be the stepping stones for their unblocking of new opportunities in the sports industry.

Moreover, the unique characteristics and demands of teaching, especially within physical education, emphasize the importance of ongoing professional development. As such, it is crucial for physical education teachers implementing Special Program in Sports (SPS) to actively participate in DepEd-sponsored scholarship programs and professional upgrading in their specialized field, including enrollment in a master's degree program in sports. These efforts enhance teaching strategies and ensure educators remain informed about the field's best practices and innovative methodologies.

Alfaidi and Elhassan (2020) cited Mokeira (2009), who characterized training workshops as structured programs to enhance instructional and professional knowledge, skills, and interests. They further underscored the necessity for field experts to thoughtfully introduce, guide, and assess training and professional development programs. These programs must comprehensively address all educational needs regularly to ensure that educators receive the essential support and resources for their professional growth.

This process leads to building appropriate human resources for the nation. Physical education teachers must show an optimistic view, interest, and enthusiasm for reskilling their teaching competencies and enable teachers to keep abreast of changes in the educational process. Thus, teachers will be aware of technological advancements and the development of curricula and instructional methods.

Besides that, the faculty also comprises seasoned professionals and industry experts whose extensive academic knowledge and real-world experience contribute to a robust learning experience. Educational programs emphasize the development of professional competencies in alignment with the standards of the teaching profession (Catalano et al., 2020).

The instructional skills of physical education (PE) teachers who implement special sports programs of the highest possible level are essential for creating an environment home to students with different needs and providing them with good educational possibilities. The research underlines the need for qualified Physical Education experts who have the competence to design and implement learning experiences that are both engaging and effective. Thus, they can offer various opportunities for students to align with the requirements of the physical activity standard compared to non-specialized teachers.

Such strategies as differentiated instruction, adjusting to different skill statuses and abilities in the performance of student tasks, and encouraging student engagement and learning outcomes at the highest level are the most effective.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the theoretical frameworks of instructional skills and competency skill theory in modern teaching by Mallillin and Mallillin (2019).

First, skills theory for instructional competency and knowledge of improved teaching practice are the basis for effective pedagogy in learning. It is concentrated on the teachers' competency and the instructional skills that will result in the modern teaching theory in the new era, which includes classroom management. It creates a scientific theory to expand and deepen the horizons of the educational field of teaching.

Secondly, the instructional skills and competency skills theory need stability in education. It defines professional development for teachers that explains sustainability competency and instructional skills in the modern teaching context.

On the one hand, the request of the instructional skills theory in modern teaching that gauges teachers' performance and instructional skills and competency level in teaching and learning has a repercussion on the educational system and comprises technical skills, innovation, and the challenges of various skills that are necessary for teachers (Mallillin & Mallillin, 2019).

Besides, some skills and competencies in the modern educational system, examined in a teaching intervention, emphasize the learning needs of students. Students meet these needs through performance, learning activities, direct instructions, and reflection. The association between the educational theory and the theory of contributions in adapting the intervention of instructional skills and competency skills for teachers in teaching and learning is also discussed herein (Mallillin, 2022). The knowledge and skills of following the teaching and learning processes' application in well-organized classroom settings are supported by this initiative (Mallillin & Laurel, 2022).

Cooperation and teamwork are needed in modern educational skills and competency as a primary basis for curriculum development, especially in the educational system's goals. Peer teaching and learning instruction can make this happen. Involving discussion, the concept of teaching and learning, and student work plans are ways to come to a clear understanding of the learning process.

Furthermore, those skills and competencies in modern teaching acknowledge the gaps, issues, and difficulties in the complicated teaching work. It thus covers the core competency elements of a sound educational system and practical training. The ones who alter the world are the teachers who help make other teachers happy in the learning process. Their performance, teaching quality, knowledge, and preparation of skills for instruction and competence in the current teaching industry determine the fate of instructors. It may be shown as a lifelong teaching ability of teachers of a professional vocation in a positive and open health state of mind and body, good speakers, and able to complete complex instructional tasks and assignments. It passes through professional development and competence, pedagogy and capacity, instructional abilities, invention, implementation, educational activities, and approaches.

Considering this, teachers' teaching methods and techniques will significantly improve their adaptability and flexibility when facing fresh educational obstacles. The strong internal drive of physical education instructors to embrace new ideas and teaching techniques helps to create an ongoing learning and professional development culture. To facilitate this, physical education teachers engage in various tasks designed to create enriching and meaningful student experiences. By addressing the diverse needs of learners, physical education teachers can cultivate an inclusive environment that supports the growth and development of all students. These efforts are associated with improved learning outcomes and the overall quality of education, ensuring that each learner effectively participates in their physical education experience and works toward reaching their potential.

Hence, the study aimed to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Moreover, the study will be a basis for a capability-building plan. The level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in

implementing the Special Program in Sports within the areas mentioned above were measured in the continuum of a 5-part scale with the following range: 5 as the highest or "very high level," 4 as "high level," three as "moderate level," 2 "low level" to 1 as the lowest or "very low level."

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special sports programs in a public secondary school in a medium school division in Central Philippines during the school year 2024-2025 as the basis for a capability-building plan.

Methodology:

This section presents the research design used, the study's respondents, data gathering instruments, the validity and reliability of the instrument, the data gathering procedure, analytical schemes, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to determine the instructional skills of Physical Education teachers in implementing the Special Program in Sports in a public secondary school in a medium-sized school Division in the Central Philippines during the first and second phases of the implementation period for School Year 2024-2025. This was concluded with the Negros Occidental National High School, Division of Negros Occidental.

According to Cole (2016), descriptive research design is a particular approach that entails observing and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any influence. Additionally, it involves gathering quantitative data that can be summed up in numerical form along a continuum, like test results or how often a person chooses to use a specific multimedia program feature. It can also describe data categories, like gender or interaction patterns when using technology in a group setting.

In this investigation, a descriptive research design was used as it had an excellent correlation with the researcher's purpose of figuring out the instructional skills of physical education teachers. At the same time, they carry out a specialized sports program. The design is suitable for capturing detailed data and representing the findings in a manner that reveals, explains, and validates the obtained information. In carrying out this method, the researcher endeavored to glean in-depth insights that would then be used as a basis for a capability-building program specifically designed to improve the performance of physical education teachers.

Respondents of the Study

The study respondents included 30 SPS students from Grade 7 and Grade 8 who were officially enrolled in the Special Program in Sports at a public secondary school within a medium-sized school division in central Philippines. Additionally, students from Grade 7 to Grade 8 SPS at Negros Occidental High School in Bacolod City were invited to complete a survey to evaluate the reliability of the study and gather important data regarding the participants' experiences and perspectives related to the program. Complete enumeration was utilized because the total number of respondents is manageable.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to their grade level.

Table 1
Distribution of the Respondents

Grade Level	Population (N)	Percentage (%)
Grade 7	15	50.0
Grade 8	15	50.0
Total	30	100.0

Data Gathering Instrument

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire to determine the level of instructional skills of Physical Education teachers in implementing the Special Program in Sports in a public secondary school in a medium-sized school Division in the Central Philippines during the school year 2024-2025 as the basis for a capability plan.

The instrument was divided into two parts. Part I of the questionnaire determined the profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, grade level, and specialized sports. Part II was the proper questionnaire, divided into three areas: curriculum, teaching, and assessment. Each area contained 10 items, and 30 items on the survey questionnaire focused on issues

that could be rated with numbers 1-5, 5 being the highest and 1 being the lowest.

Furthermore, each description was interpreted using the five-point Likert scale, which contains the following scores: 5 as a very high level, 4 as a high level, 3 as a medium level, 2 as a low level, and 1 as a very low level.

Validity

According to Shields (2015), validity can be defined as the degree to which a notion is accurate or the degree to which test findings and interpretations are supported by the specific purpose for which the test is designed. The research underwent face and content validation by a jury of three experts in the field using the criteria set forth by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates. The questionnaire was meticulously crafted and presented to three esteemed jurors, each bringing expertise in various sports disciplines. These individuals, distinguished by their certifications as technical officials, coaches, trainers, and MAPEH (Music, Arts, PE, and Health) educators, played a critical role in validating the questionnaire's content.

Using the Good and Scates scale, the interpretations of the validation score were as follows: excellent (4.04-5.000), very good (3.28-4.03), good (2.52-3.27), poor (2.52-3.27), very poor (1.00-1.75).

The validation score for this study was 4.93, which was interpreted as excellent and, therefore, considered valid. The results were highly commendable in providing the final validation score to complete the validation procedure.

Reliability

According to Usman (2016), reliability refers to the degree of support for the interpretation of test results, which varies based on the specific purpose of the test. A reliability instrument, Cronbach's Alpha, was used to ensure the test was reliable. Cronbach's Alpha measures internal consistency, or how closely a group of things relates to one another.

Reliability was established through a dry run with thirty (30) Grade 7 and Grade 8 SPS learners enrolled in the Special Program in Sports in Negros Occidental High School-Bacolod City, Division of Negros Occidental. The obtained value of the tests must be between 0.70 and 1.00 to be reliable (Bluman, 2017), cited in Arcenas (2021). The computed Alpha on the instructional skills of physical education teachers was .956, interpreted as "excellence," and is therefore deemed reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher adopted several steps and procedures to abide by research ethics for the study to be smoothly carried out. The researcher initially obtained permission to conduct the study by submitting a formal letter to the school heads. Upon receipt of their reply confirming the request, a signed letter was forwarded to the department heads for further approval to distribute the survey questionnaires.

To guarantee that the student respondents' participation is voluntary, the procedure implements an informed consent waiver that is included in the survey questionnaire before the start of the study, as the student respondents are classified as minors. The research method illustrates the indispensable part of consent and ethical principles while doing research with the young ones, as it demonstrates the necessity of the students' autonomy being respected; however, guardians need to be a part of the consent process to the extent that they give their consent. After the reliability test for the research instrument was carried out through Google Forms, the researcher administered the instrument to the respondents on the scheduled day and time. Before distributing the survey questionnaire to participants, the researcher clearly outlined the respective sections and areas in the document. Such a detailed step ensured that respondents were clear about what was expected. The researcher outlined that if respondents were to complete every question, then the responses from each question would be used as valuable data.

The data gathered from the respondents' responses were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allowed computer processing, statistical derivations, and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to process the encoded data on the computer.

Research Ethics Protocol

Every research project must prioritize the protection of the respondents by adhering to the relevant ethical guidelines. People cannot be forced to participate in research to uphold the principle of voluntary participation (Trochim, 2021, as cited in Bersales, 2021). Consent should be given freely to them (voluntarily), the subject should understand what they are asked to do, and participants must be able to consent. (Arifin, 2018)

The respondents received assurances of the confidentiality of the results, including the promise that no one not directly involved in the study could access their personal information. The researcher was also vigilant about minimizing the risk of physical and psychological harm to participants throughout the research process.

Analytical Schemes

The study used two (2) analytical schemes, descriptive and comparative, based on the study's objectives.

Objective No. 1: The descriptive-analytical scheme was used to determine the respondent's profile in terms of sex, grade level, and specialized sports.

Objective No. 2, the descriptive-analytical scheme, was used to determine the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in the curriculum, teaching, and assessment in implementing the special program in sports.

Objective No. 3, the descriptive-analytical scheme, was used to determine the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports as a basis for a capability-building plan when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 4, the comparative-analytical scheme, was used to determine the significant difference in the instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing the special program in sports when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Statistical Tools

Various statistical tools were utilized to analyze data to address this study's objectives.

Objective No. 1: The frequency count and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, grade level, and specialized sports.

Data that indicates the proportion of observations for each data point or set of data points is displayed using a percentage frequency distribution. It is a valuable way to convey the relative frequency of data, including survey replies (Carole, 2016).

Objective No. 2: The mean was used to determine the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing the Special Program in Sports according to curriculum, teaching, and assessment.

The mean or average used to determine the central tendency of the relevant data is known as the statistical mean. To calculate it, tally up all the data points in a population, then divide the total by the number of points. The average or mean is the resultant figure (Assignment Point, 2022).

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very High Level
3.50-4.49	High Level
2.50-3.49	Moderate Level
1.50-2.49	Low level
1.00-1.49	Very Low Level

Objective No. 3: The mean was used to determine the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports as a basis for a capability-building plan when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

This evaluation seeks to quantify their professional development and expertise in handling sports events.

Objective No. 4: The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine the significant difference in the instructional skills of physical education teachers who ultimately contribute to the effectiveness of the Special Program in Sports when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

A nonparametric test for the null hypothesis is the Mann-Whitney U-Test. The probability of a randomly selected value from one being less than or greater than a randomly picked value from another sample is equal. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a comparable nonparametric test applied to dependent samples, can ascertain if two independent samples were drawn from populations with the same distribution (Clarkson, 2015). It is possible to presume at least one significant difference and reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than the commonly accepted alpha risk of five (5) percent (0.05) (Buthman, 2019, referenced in Acumabig, 2021).

Depending on the significance threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis is either accepted or rejected. Null hypothesis rejection occurs if the p-value is less than 0.05, while acceptance occurs if the p-value is more than the significance level of 0.05.

Results and Discussion:

Profile of the Respondents according to Sex, Grade Level, and Specialized Sports

Table 2
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	21	70.00
	Female	9	30.00
	Total	30	100

Grade Level	Grade 7	15	50.00
	Grade 8	15	50.00
	Total	30	100
Specialized Sports	Individual/Dual	11	36.67
	Team	19	63.33
	Total	30	100

The study's first objective is to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, grade level, and specialized sports. Regarding sex, there were 21, or 70.00%, male respondents and 9, or 30.00%, female respondents. Regarding the grade level, 15, or 50.00% of the students, belonged to Grade 7, while 15, or 50.00%, belonged to Grade 8. Regarding specialized sports, 11, or 36.67%, took individual or dual sports, while 19, or 63.33%, took team sports.

The table revealed that most respondents belong to the male category, and both grade levels have the same number of respondents. The majority of the respondents engaged in team sports. This implies that higher male participation in special sports programs reflects a complex interplay of innate biological advantages, stronger male motivation for competition, greater interest in sports, and social factors, including access and cultural expectations that limit females' sports involvement due to some practical barriers encountered that collectively contribute to the low percentage of female enrolled in a sports program. Specifically, the study indicates that boys prefer team sports such as football, basketball, and volleyball, which are physically demanding and involve direct interaction and collaboration with teammates. These sports satisfy boys' inclination toward competitive and dynamic group activities, whereas girls prefer individual or less competitive sports that emphasize social aspects differently. They like to engage in team sports where they can manifest teamwork, collaborative effort, and camaraderie whenever they have training and gameplay.

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Curriculum, Teaching, and Assessment

Table 3

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in the Curriculum

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>		
1. manifests a wide range of knowledge and skills in the specific sports discipline covered in the special program.	4.60	Very High Level
2. simplifies content, activities, and assessments by providing examples in the local context for learners' better understanding.	4.40	High Level
3. integrates the five learning strands of physical education (body management, movement skills, games and sports, rhythms and dances, and physical fitness) into the curriculum.	4.37	High Level
4. works collaboratively with colleagues to address the learning gaps by creating activities for various skill levels and providing the necessary support to make learning experiences meaningful for all learners.	4.33	High Level
5. applies innovative teaching techniques that cater to learners' unique learning needs, which <u>enhances</u> the development of sports skills.	4.20	High Level
6. creates and executes an engaging sports training program that aligns with the objectives and standards of a specialized sports initiative, ensuring SPS learners reach their optimal potential.	4.33	High Level
7. incorporates engaging teaching aids, such as lively demonstrations, captivating videos, and interactive games, to boost learning and active participation.	4.20	High Level
8. uses effective teaching strategies that meet learners' needs and enhance understanding, participation, and achievement.	4.33	High Level
9. provides essential resources and sufficient space necessary for the successful conduct of practical skills and sports activities.	4.43	High Level
10. establishes a safe and secure learning environment by ensuring that all learners adhere to the guidelines and procedures during game training and play.	4.47	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level

Table 3 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing a special program in sports in the curriculum. The overall mean score is 4.37, interpreted as "high level."

Item 1, which states, "manifest a wide range of knowledge and skills in the specific sports discipline covered in the special program," got the highest mean score of 4.60, interpreted as "high level." Meanwhile, items 5 and 7 states, "applies innovative teaching techniques that cater to learners' unique learning needs, which enhances the development of sports skills," and "incorporates a variety of engaging teaching aids, such as lively demonstrations, captivating videos, and interactive games, to boost learning and active participation. Both items got the lowest mean score of 4.20, interpreted as "high level."

The result suggests that some physical education teachers prefer to use traditional methods of teaching in the delivery of instructions on the content of the lesson, strategies and techniques applied in the teaching and learning process, and even in assessing the SPS learners based on the learners' needs and interests.

This conclusion was supported by the contemporary movement towards competency-based teacher education, recognizing that 21st-century competencies are vital for successfully navigating present and future challenges. These competencies are influenced by technological advancements that continuously transform workplace dynamics and lifestyles (Caena & Redecker, 2019). Additionally, the study of Bantilan (2024) showed dynamic, experienced, and empowering SPS teachers who prioritize learners' needs, create innovative teaching methods, and adapt teaching strategies for 21st-century success.

Table 4

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Teaching

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>		
1. provides explicit instructions, uses simple language, and incorporates analogies to help learners understand complex concepts more easily.	4.43	High Level
2. incorporate fitness and wellness, such as personal health, well-being, and movement competence, that contribute to the overall wellness of the SPS learners.	4.40	High Level
3. integrates different teaching strategies (e.g., drills, games, exercises) into the lessons.	4.50	Very High Level
4. adopts the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) Model to foster a deep understanding of sports, prioritizing tactical and strategic aspects associated with the games.	3.90	High Level
5. employs cooperative learning strategies that encourage teamwork and peer interaction, enhancing social skills.	4.30	High Level
6. analyzes student data in adjusting teachers' strategies, ensuring that lessons align with student capabilities and learning objectives.	4.33	High Level
7. encourages students to set and achieve personal goals in the context of sports.	4.33	High Level
8. maintains a safe and conducive environment while ensuring student engagement in physical activities.	4.30	High Level
9. conducts remediation classes for students at risk in academic subjects to maintain the required grades.	3.90	High Level
10. utilizes technology to create interactive lessons and provide individualized instruction, fostering better learner engagement.	4.23	High Level
Overall Mean	4.26	High Level

Table 4 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing the special program in sports in the teaching area. The overall mean score is 4.26, interpreted as "high level."

Item 3, which states "integrates different teaching strategies (e.g., drills, games, exercises) into the lessons," got the highest mean score of 4.50, interpreted as "very high level." Items 4 and 9, which state "adopts the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) Model to foster a deep understanding of sports prioritizing tactical and strategic aspects associated with the games," and "conducts remediation classes for the students who are at risk in academic subjects to maintain the required grades," both got the lowest mean score of 3.90, interpreted as "high level."

The result suggests that teachers must find time to be resourceful and updated on the new teaching techniques of sports to make learning more meaningful to the lives of the learners by embracing the latest trends in teaching. Due to time constraints and focused more on specialized subjects in the sports curriculum, the physical education teachers opted to give remediation classes to those SPS learners who were at risk in their academic subjects. The study concurred with the K-10 MATATAG Curriculum that each learner will develop higher-order thinking skills by adopting the TGFU model in physical education, which significantly enhances learners' tactical and strategic understanding of sports by engaging them in game-like situations that emphasize decision-making, problem-solving, and critical thinking over rote skill acquisition. By focusing on tactical awareness before technical skill refinement, TGFU prepares

learners for effective sports participation, lifelong physical activity appreciation, and inclusive learning experiences tailored to diverse learner needs.

Mandigo et al. (2019) concluded that Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) can effectively promote specific components of physical literacy development in students, including fitness skills and active participation. The result highlights that SPS learners who were lagging behind their academic subjects will be given an independent cooperative learning session by the physical education teachers as mandated in the DepEd Order No.25 S. 2015, which states that Physical education teachers must be devoted to providing support to learner-athletes through Independent Cooperative Learning (ICL) sessions to enhance retention in the program. This approach can assist students in understanding competencies with which they have had difficulties, ensuring that all learners stay engaged in their education. By addressing specific areas of challenge, educators can offer targeted support that facilitates student achievement and promotes an inclusive learning environment. Despite this, there are still unresolved issues, as not every aspect of the subject has been comprehensively explored.

Furthermore, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued various orders and memoranda regarding remediation programs. DepEd Order 8, s. 2015 mandates implementing the Remedial Program for students who failed one or two subjects. It outlines the program for students who have not met the required competencies. SPS learners must be given intervention through remediation classes by physical education teachers to retain and increase their academic grades, showing that targeted interventions significantly improve performance.

Additionally, mandatory remediation periods have been shown to boost passing rates, particularly when combined with tailored study plans and faculty support. By implementing school-based remediation, SPS learners can ensure that they master essential competencies, reduce grade retention rates, foster equitable academic success, and progress to the next grade level in the Special Program in Sports until they graduate.

Table 5

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Assessment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>		
1. monitors and document the learner's daily progress toward mastering skills and concepts.	3.90	High Level
2. incorporates various assessment tools, such as skill tests, peer observation checklists, self-assessments, portfolios, event-task projects, and fitness concept application assignments.	4.10	High Level
3. integrates multiple competencies that are designed to be flexible, allowing learners to complete over time using available resources.	4.00	High Level
4. assigns tasks such as creating a personal fitness plan or leading a warm-up routine for a discipline that integrates knowledge, planning, and execution.	4.23	High Level
5. utilizes technology, such as mobile applications for performance tracking, digital tools to analyze performance, or video analysis for skill improvement and feedback.	3.97	High Level
6. encourages students to reflect on their performance using rubrics or journals and assess peers during group activities to promote accountability and self-appreciation.	4.20	High Level
7. plans or designs the Sports Fest Program to showcase every learner's capability in their specialized discipline at the end of the quarter.	4.20	High Level
8. provides timely and appropriate student feedback, essential for developing motor and tactical skills.	4.00	High Level
9. encourages students to join sports clinics and engage in any tournament in a specific specialized sports discipline.	3.83	High Level
10. presents the rubrics with clarity, empowering students to strive for excellence and give their best on the preferred task to perform during practical skills.	4.17	High Level
Overall Mean	4.06	High Level

Table 5 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing a special program in sports in the assessment area. The overall mean score is 4.06, interpreted as "high level."

Item 4, which states, "assigns tasks such as creating a personal fitness plan or leading a warm-up routine for a specific discipline, which integrates knowledge, planning, and execution," got the highest mean score of 4.23, interpreted as "high level" While item 9 which states "encourages students to join sports clinics and engage in any tournament in a specific specialized sports discipline" got the lowest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as "high level." The table indicates that some physical education teachers do not encourage SPS learners to participate in sports clinics and open tournaments. This lack of encouragement may impact the learners' opportunities to become

champions in their respective sports disciplines, as well as their ability to enhance their skills and build self-confidence during gameplay. Supporting the needs and interests of learners can contribute to their development as productive individuals.

A relevant study published in 2022 investigated the role of SPS in the athletic activities and performance of student-athletes and the importance of joining sports clinics and open tournaments for the Special Program in Sports. Athletic activities were reported as high in training performance, regular sports participation, and health status and very high in theoretical knowledge, athletic potential, focus and discipline, resiliency and humility, and harmony and unity.

In summary, the study by the author(s) of the 2022 article on SPS learners highlights the importance of structured sports programs, coaching, and competition opportunities such as clinics and open tournaments in fostering athletic and personal development among student-athletes.

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Curriculum, Teaching, and Assessment when grouped according to Sex, Grade Level, and Specialized Sports

Table 6

Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male			Female		
	Mean	Interpretation		Mean	Interpretation	
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>						
1. manifests a wide range of knowledge and skills in the specific sports discipline covered in the special program.	4.57	Very Level	High	4.67	Very Level	High
2. simplifies content, activities, and assessments by providing examples in the local context for learners' better understanding.	4.29	High Level		4.67	Very Level	High
3. integrates the five learning strands of physical education (body management, movement skills, games and sports, rhythms and dances, and physical fitness) into the curriculum.	4.33	High Level		4.44	High Level	
4. works collaboratively with colleagues to address the learning gaps by creating activities for various skill levels and providing the necessary support to make learning experiences meaningful for all learners.	4.38	High Level		4.22	High Level	
5. applies innovative teaching techniques that cater to learners' unique learning needs, which enhances the development of sports skills.	4.19	High Level		4.22	High Level	
6. creates and executes an engaging sports training program that aligns with the objectives and standards of a specialized sports initiative, ensuring SPS learners reach their optimal potential.	4.38	High Level		4.22	High Level	
7. incorporates engaging teaching aids, such as lively demonstrations, captivating videos, and interactive games, to boost learning and active participation.	4.24	High Level		4.11	High Level	
8. uses effective teaching strategies that meet learners' needs and enhance understanding, participation, and achievement.	4.19	High Level		4.67	Very Level	High
9. provides essential resources and sufficient space necessary for the successful conduct of practical skills and sports activities.	4.38	High Level		4.56	Very Level	High
10. establishes a safe and secure learning environment by ensuring that all learners adhere to the guidelines and procedures during game training and play.	4.38	High Level		4.67	Very Level	High
Overall Mean	4.33	High Level		4.44	High Level	

Table 6 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports in the area of curriculum when grouped according to sex. The overall mean scores were 4.33 for the male group and 4.44 for the female group. Both were interpreted as "high level." Item 1, which states "manifests a wide range of knowledge and skills in the specific sports discipline covered in the special program," got the highest mean score of 4.57 for the male group and 4.67 for the female group. Both were interpreted as "very high level." Items

2, 8, and 10 also got the highest mean scores as assessed by the female group, interpreted as "very high level," which states "simplify content, activities, and assessments by providing examples in the local context for learners' better understanding," "uses effective teaching strategies that meet learners' needs and enhance understanding, participation, and achievement" and, "establishes a safe and secure learning environment by ensuring that all learners adhere to the guidelines and procedures during game training and play."

Meanwhile, items 5 and 8 states, "applies innovative teaching techniques that cater to learners' unique learning needs, which enhances the development of sports skills" and "uses effective teaching strategies that meet learners' needs and enhance understanding, participation, and achievement" got the lowest mean score of 4.19 for the male group, interpreted as "high level." Item 7, which states, "incorporates a variety of engaging teaching aids, such as lively demonstrations, captivating videos, and interactive games, to boost learning and active participation," got the lowest mean score of 4.11 for the female group, interpreted as "high level." The findings indicate that physical education teachers may struggle with integrating technology and online platforms into their teaching practices. Despite the City government providing all educators with laptops and televisions to facilitate a more modern and efficient teaching approach, many still rely on traditional instructional methods. This suggests a disconnect between available resources and actual teaching practices. Furthermore, the preferences exhibited by physical education teachers in their instructional strategies are influenced more by their methodologies than by their student's diverse needs and interests. As a result, using technology as a motivating tool to foster greater student engagement and participation remains limited, hindering the potential for a more dynamic and interactive learning environment.

It explores integrating technology into the classroom and its role in improving the learning experience and increasing student engagement and outcomes, focusing on the importance of effective teaching to build a positive learning environment and enhance the performance of teachers and learners. He emphasizes that combining technology and innovative teaching strategies is the key to educational excellence in the current era. According to Alaa (2024), adopting electronic teaching methods and interactive learning methods not only facilitates distance learning but also provides essential skills like communication and critical thinking. By embracing interactive teaching approaches, leveraging technology, and promoting self-directed learning, educational institutions can foster a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in teaching and learning. Teachers can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that suits learning styles and preferences using modern technology and teaching strategies such as reflection and problem-solving. Enhancing students' readiness and self-teaching through interactive training methods is of utmost importance to prepare future teachers for the challenges of today's educational system.

Table 7
Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Teaching when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>				
1. provides explicit instructions, uses simple language, and incorporates analogies to help learners understand complex concepts more easily.	4.33	High Level	4.67	Very High Level
2. incorporate fitness and wellness, such as personal health, well-being, and movement competence, that contribute to the overall wellness of the SPS learners.	4.29	High Level	4.67	Very High Level
3. integrates different teaching strategies (e.g., drills, games, exercises) into the lessons.	4.33	High Level	4.89	Very High Level
4. adopts the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) Model to foster a deep understanding of sports, prioritizing tactical and strategic aspects associated with the games.	3.86	High Level	4.00	High Level
5. employs cooperative learning strategies that encourage teamwork and peer interaction, enhancing social skills.	4.24	High Level	4.44	High Level
6. analyzes student data in adjusting teachers' strategies, ensuring that lessons align with student capabilities and learning objectives.	4.29	High Level	4.44	High Level

7. encourages students to set and achieve personal goals in the context of sports.	4.24	High Level	4.56	Very High Level	High
8. maintains a safe and conducive environment while ensuring student engagement in physical activities.	4.24	High Level	4.44	High Level	
9. conducts remediation classes for students at risk in academic subjects to maintain the required grades.	3.76	High Level	4.22	High Level	
10. utilizes technology to create interactive lessons and provide individualized instruction, fostering better learner engagement.	4.24	High Level	4.22	High Level	
Overall Mean	4.18	High Level	4.46	High Level	

Table 7 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports in teaching when grouped according to sex. The overall mean scores were 4.18 for the male group and 4.46 for the female group. Both were interpreted as "high level." Items 1 and 3, which state "provides clear instructions, use simple language, and incorporates analogies to help learners understand complex concepts more easily," and "integrates different teaching strategies (e.g., drills, games, exercises) into the lessons," got the highest mean score of 4.33 for the male group, interpreted as "high level." Item 3, which states "integrates different teaching strategies (e.g., drills, games, exercises) into the lessons," got the highest mean score of 4.89 for the female group, interpreted as "very high level." Meanwhile, item 9, which states, "conducts remediation classes for the students who are at risk in academic subjects to maintain the required grades," got the lowest mean score of 3.76 for the male group. In contrast, item 4, which states, "adopts the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) Model to foster a deep understanding of sports prioritizing tactical and strategic aspects associated with the games," got the lowest mean score of 4.00 as assessed by the female group. Both were interpreted as "high level." The data presented in the table highlights the sentiments of most respondents regarding physical education teachers, indicating that their teaching methods are perceived as outdated.

The findings revealed a significant lack of familiarity among these teachers with the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) Model, an innovative approach designed to enhance student engagement and comprehension in sports. Furthermore, it was observed that the planned intervention program, aimed at supporting students with low academic performance, was neither implemented nor effectively executed by these educators. This oversight suggests a gap in the ability of physical education teachers to assist struggling learners better. The MATATAG Curriculum supports implementing the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) Model in physical education classes and the special program in sports. Contextualization and localization may be incorporated, provided they align with the learning competencies. This teaching approach emphasizes learning sports by playing modified versions of the games, with a focus on tactical understanding and decision-making before skill development. The model is beneficial in schools with limited resources during practical assessments. Physical education teachers can also monitor students' academic progress in the Special Program in Sports (SPS). Interventions will be provided at the end of afternoon classes for learners identified as at risk.

Table 8
Level of Instructional Skills of Physical Education Teachers in Implementing Special Programs in Sports in Assessment when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A Physical Education Teacher in the Special Program in Sports...</i>				
1. monitors and document the learner's daily progress toward mastering skills and concepts.	3.90	High Level	3.89	High Level
2. incorporates various assessment tools, such as skill tests, peer observation checklists, self-assessments, portfolios, event-task projects, and fitness concept application assignments.	3.95	High Level	4.44	High Level
3. integrates multiple competencies that are designed to be flexible, allowing learners to complete over time using available resources.	4.00	High Level	4.00	High Level
4. assigns tasks such as creating a personal fitness plan or leading a	4.19	High Level	4.33	High Level

warm-up routine for a discipline that integrates knowledge, planning, and execution.				
5. utilizes technology, such as mobile applications for performance tracking, and uses digital tools to analyze performance or video analysis for skill improvement and feedback.	3.86	High Level	4.22	High Level
6. encourages students to reflect on their performance using rubrics or journals and assess peers during group activities to promote accountability and self-appreciation.	4.19	High Level	4.22	High Level
7. plans/designs the Sports Fest Program to showcase every learner's capability in their specialized discipline at the end of the quarter.	4.24	High Level	4.11	High Level
8. provides timely and appropriate student feedback, essential for developing motor and tactical skills.	3.81	High Level	4.44	High Level
9. encourages students to join sports clinics and engage in any tournament in a specific specialized sports discipline.	3.71	High Level	4.11	High Level
10. presents the rubrics with clarity, empowering students to strive for excellence and give their best on the preferred task to perform during practical skills.	4.19	High Level	4.11	High Level
Overall Mean	4.00	High Level	4.19	High Level

Table 8 shows the level of instructional skills of physical education teachers in implementing special programs in sports in assessment when grouped according to sex. The overall mean scores were 4.00 for the male group and 4.19 for the female group. Both were interpreted as "high level." Item 7, which states "plans or designs the Sports Fest Program to showcase every learner's capability in their specialized discipline at the end of the quarter" got the highest mean score of 4.24 for the male group and items 2 and 8 which state "incorporates a variety of assessment tools, such as skill tests, peer observation checklists, self-assessments, portfolios, event-task projects, and fitness concept application assignments" and "provides timely and appropriate feedback for the students, which is essential for the development of motor and tactical skills" got the highest mean score of 4.44. Both were interpreted as "high level." Meanwhile, item 9, which states "encourages students to join sports clinics and engage in any tournament in a specific specialized sports discipline," got the lowest mean score of 3.71 for the male group, and item 1, which states "monitors and documents the learner's daily progress toward mastery of skills and concepts" got the lowest mean score of 3.89 as assessed by the female group. Both were interpreted as "high level."

The findings reveal a significant gap in the involvement of SPS learners in physical education activities, particularly in the sports clinic and open tournaments. This lack of engagement stems from the overwhelming demands placed on physical education teachers, who have not been afforded the necessary time to facilitate student participation. As a result, they have struggled to effectively monitor each SPS learner's progress, thereby missing critical opportunities to provide individualized feedback on their mastery of the skills and concepts taught during lessons. As concluded in DepEd Order No. 2015, this policy mandated the utilization of various evidence-based classroom assessment practices. As stated in No. 27 provisions, teachers play a crucial role in gauging and monitoring the learning progress of their learners and guiding them toward realizing their full potential. Teachers are encouraged to optimize the use of technology in assessing learning at any learning phase. Implement the provisions to guide them in effectively evaluating their learners' academic progress.

The lesson plans must reflect instructional decisions to address these challenges. This includes implementing individualized monitoring strategies for each learner and developing a comprehensive plan of action to promote the students' overall welfare and development. Such an approach would ensure that each SPS learner receives the support they need to thrive in their specialized sports program journey.

Conclusion:

The study found that physical education teachers implementing the Special Program in Sports (SPS) demonstrated generally high instructional skills across curriculum, teaching, and assessment, with particularly strong knowledge in specific sports events and teaching strategies. However, improvements are needed in adopting innovative methods such as the Teaching Games for Understanding (TGFU) model, enhancing digital skills, and using Independent Cooperative Learning (ICL) to support academically at-risk learners. Teachers showed challenges in consistently monitoring student progress using technology and providing timely feedback. No significant differences were found in instructional skills based on sex, grade level, or sports specialization, indicating a uniform skill level across these variables. The use of teaching aids was seen as beneficial in engaging students, though remediation and academic feedback remain insufficient. Positive attitudes toward professional development suggest potential growth through seminars, collaborative expertise, and further training. Recommendations include conducting workshops on digitizing lessons, benchmarking best practices, continuous ICT training, embracing the TGFU model, and encouraging student participation in sports clinics and tournaments. Sustained professional development and monitoring are essential to maintain and improve instructional effectiveness. Future research should explore additional variables affecting instructional skills to further enhance SPS implementation.

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References:

- Arcenas, M.N.B. (2021). Technical and Innovative Skills of Araling Panlipunan (AP) Teachers: Basis for a Proposed Training Plan (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.
- Ariola, E., Abao, G., & Bautista, M. (2025). Teachers' Motivation, Difficulties and Performance in Teaching MAPEH in the New Normal. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 2(6), 509-523. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15662491>
- Baert, H. (2011). The Integration of Technology within Physical Education Teacher Education: Perceptions of the Faculty. Graduate Theses and Dissertations Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/etd/203>
- Bantilan, E. (2024). Teachers 21st Century Skills Special Program in Sports Curriculum Volume 3, No.1
- Bersales, A.R.(2021). Program Implementation of the Physical Fitness Test In The New Normal (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.
- Coronel, WJ. H.(2021). Implementation of Senior High School Sports Track: Basis for Intervention Plan (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.
- Donaire, E.R. (2024). Teaching Strategies in Physical Education. A Literature Review of Practices in the United States, China, and Nigeria, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*. Volume 5, pp.9-12
- Gosset, M. Ed.D..(2021) Four Favorite Physical Education Instructional Strategies Recommended by Teachers
- Hussein, A. A., PhD. (2024). Innovative Teaching Methods Enhancing Engagement and Learning Outcomes
- International Journal of Sport, Exercise and Health Research* (2017) Vol 1 pp. 61-65
- Larosa, J. R. (2023). Teachers' Competence In Relation to Their Information and Communication Technology Utilization (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.
- Liangfa L. (2024). Level of Practice on The Instructional Delivery and Sports Management Among Physical Education Teachers, *International Journal of Education and Humanities* Volume 13, No.3
- Mishra, P., & Mehta, R. (2022). The role of digital resources in professional teacher development: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 40(3), 87-102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939X.2022.2085796>

OECD (2019). Making Physical Education Dynamic and Inclusive for 2030: International Curriculum Analysis

Pestano & Ibarra. (2021). Assessment on the Implementation of Special Program in Sports and Student-Athletes' Performance in Sports Competition, *International Journal of Human Movement and Sports Sciences* Vol. 9, No. 4, pp. 791 – 796

Sabillo, S., Tiauzon, M. J., Bautista, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Technical skills and competence of sports officiating officials: Basis for an action plan. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(11), 11-51. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v11i11.ss01>

Santillan, R., Dejito, M., & Bautista, M. (2025). Schools' Sports Coordinators' Compliance, Commitment, and Difficulties in Sports for All Policy. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRIS)*, 2(6), 224-235. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15631329>

Sung, Y. T., & Hwang, G. J. (2023). Enhancing Teachers' Engagement with Technology-based Instructional Materials: A case study *Educational Research & Development*, 45(1), 29-47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-023-101234>

Tanate, R. (2019). Teaching Skills of MAPEH Teachers in Relation To The Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.

Philippine Social Science Journal (2019). The Implementation of Special Sports Program in a Public Secondary School Volume 2, No.2

Yam, LM.S. (2019). Teachers' Competence in Teaching Music in Relation to Student's Performance (Unpublished Thesis). STI, West Negros University.

UNESCO (2015). Teaching and Learning for A Sustainable Future
http://www.unesco.org/education/tlsf/mods/theme_d/mod24.html?